

and the other is worse, or that only one and no more should be used to get positive results. The best option is to use a mix of technologies. So, the educational process mainly consists of a class-lesson system.

REFERENCES

1. Andreev A.A. Vedenie v distansionnoe obuchenie. M., 1997.
2. Belozubov A.V. Sistema distansionnogo obucheniya Moodle: uchebno-metodicheskoe posobie / A.V. Belozubov, D.G. Nikolaev. SPb: f-t ITiP SPbGU ITMO, 2007.
3. Vladimirova L. Distantsionnoe obuchenie inostrannym yazykam // Lambert academic publishing house. 2017.
4. Dobrydina T.I., Maslennikova O.G., Nadezhdina E.Yu. "Perspective use of the virtual educational platform moodle v obucheni inostrannym zykam" // Journal: Vestnik Kemerovskogo gosudarstvennogo universiteta, 2014, No. 3 (59) T. 2.

CLASSIFICATION OF ENGLISH DIALECTS

To'lqinova Nastarin

Uzbekistan State World Languages University

Faculty of English Philology

E-mail: nastarintolqinova05@gmail.com

Abstract. The paper is devoted to regional and dialectal variations of modern English in its British (Northern and Southern), American, Canadian, Australian and New Zealand variants on phonological, lexical-semantic and grammatical levels.

Keywords. *variant, dialect, accent.*

Introduction. The wide spread of the English language in the world communication has been stimulated by the rapid development of international,

Languages, culture, and translation in modern linguistics: comparative approaches

economic, scientific, and cultural relations which is called by the necessity to study the language intermediary. For a long time, English has been studied in its well-known form – BBC / RP which received the status of national standard in the UK. Under the modern circumstances when contacts have become more personal it appears to be not enough to know the refined version of the standardized English language. People become more interested in local, regional, and social variations of language which they hear every day in different parts of the world. The varieties of English attract attention not only for practical purposes but scientific cognitive too.

Main part. In our turn, we would like to pay our attention to three major differences in variation of English: phonological, lexical semantic, and structural grammatical as well as to consider the reasons of its origin. Traditionally, British dialectologists divide all variants of English into an English-based group that comprises E-E, Welsh E, Scottish E, Northern Ireland E, Australian E, New Zealand E, and an American-based group that comprises Am E and Canadian E. The main accents grouping within England are between Northern England and Southern England. Northern England includes the northeast England dialects. Northern English shows Viking influence because the area was all north of the Danelaw. The distinctive phonetic features of Northern English belong the following: using of [u] and [u:] instead of [] and [u], e.g.: luck [luk], look [lu:k], [a] instead of [æ], e.g.: cat [cat], trap [trap], monophthongs [e:] and [o:] instead of diphthons [ei] and [ou], like in face and goat. Some dialect words used across the North are listed in extended editions of the Oxford Dictionary with a marker “North England”, e.g.: ginnell and snicket for “specific types of alleyways”, to fettle – “to organize”, or the use of while to mean “until”. The best-known Northern words are nowt “nothing”, owt “anything”, summat “something”. The “present historical” is named after the speech of the northern region. Instead of saying I said to him, users would say I said to him, or instead of I went up there, they would say I go up there.

Languages, culture, and translation in modern linguistics: comparative approaches

Dialects can be defined as “sub-forms of languages which are, in general, mutually comprehensible”. English speakers from different countries and regions use a variety of different accents (systems of pronunciation) as well as various localized words and grammatical constructions. Many different dialects can be identified based on these factors. Dialects can be classified at broader or narrower levels: within a broad national or regional dialect, various more localised sub-dialects can be identified, and so on. The combination of differences in pronunciation and the use of local words may make some English dialects almost unintelligible to speakers from other regions without any prior exposure. The major native dialects of English are often divided by linguists into three general categories: the British Isles dialects, those of North America, and those of Australasia. Dialects can be associated not only with place but also with particular social groups. Within a given English-speaking country, there is a form of the language considered to be Standard English: the Standard English of different countries differ and can themselves be considered dialects. Standard English is often associated with the more educated layers of society as well as more formal registers.

Conclusion. The research material leads us to the conclusion that the origin of the English language variation is deeply motivated by historical processes and events which took place in English-speaking countries. In the case of local differences in the territory of contemporary, they result from the influence of Viking dominance in earlier times (in the North) and are concerned development of education and science (on the Southern territories). Regional varieties are much dependent on the national realities of countries-receivers of colonists from England and Ireland. The above-mentioned reasons brought the objective changes in the diversification of English talk on all language levels: phonological, morphological, lexical, and grammatical.

REFERENCES

1. A Handbook of Varieties of English / Ed. by M. De Gruyter et al. – The Hague: Mouton de Gruyter, Cop. 2018.
2. Apton C., Widdowson J.D.A. An Atlas of English Dialects / C. Apton, J.D.A. Widdowson. – Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2016.
3. Boberg Ch. The English in Canada / Ch. Boberg. – Cambridge : Cambridge University Press. – URL : ebookamerican_accent_training.pdf
4. Burrige K., Mulder J.G. English in Australia and New Zealand: an introduction to its history, structure and use / K. Burrige, J.G. Mulder. – Oxford University Press, 2019.

APPLICATIONS OF CORPUS LINGUISTICS IN LANGUAGE EDUCATION AND CURRICULUM DESIGN

Ulashova Shahzoda Berdiyori qizi

Student, UzSWLU English Philology faculty

Tashkent, Uzbekistan

Ulashovashahzoda407@gmail.com

***Abstract.** By shedding light on how language is used in everyday situations, corpus linguistics - the study of language using sizable text collections, or corpora - has significantly impacted language instruction. The application of corpus linguistics to curriculum design, discourse analysis, pronunciation, grammar instruction, and vocabulary acquisition is examined in this article. Corpus linguistics aids in the acquisition of pertinent language skills for everyday conversation by incorporating real-world language data into instruction*

***Keywords.** Data-driven learning (DDL), corpus-based learning, vocabulary selection, grammar patterns, lexical analysis, error analysis, genre analysis, frequency analysis, collocations, and authentic language input.*